

Paper 13

**TRANSFORMATIONAL REFORMS IN TEACHER EDUCATION IN THE
CONTEXT OF NEP- 2020**

Kavitha Pious

(Research Scholar, Department of Education, Srinivas University, Mangalore, Karnataka,
India) Email: kavitha.pious100@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The Education system of a country is a true indicator of its economic and social progress. Governments all over the world place a major emphasis on education policy. There is a global pressure on increasing attention on the outcomes of educational policies and their impact on social and economic development. Recently Government of India announced its new Education policy which is grounded on the recommendations by an expert committee supervised by Dr. Kasturirangan, Former chairman of the Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO). The National Education Policy 2020 envisions an India centered education system that contributes directly to transforming our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high quality education to all. The development of a nation depends upon the kind of education it provides to its teachers. Teachers truly shape the future of our children and therefore shape the future of our nation. Though the education policy has impacted school and college education equally, this paper mainly focuses on NEP-2020 and its impact on Teacher Education. The study also outlines the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect the existing education system. Finally, some suggestions are proposed for its effective implementation towards achieving its objectives.

Keywords: Teacher Education, National education policy 2020, NEP-2020

INTRODUCTION

The National Policy on Education (NPE) is a policy formulated by the Government of India to promote education amongst India's people. The policy is a comprehensive framework for elementary education to higher education as well as vocational training in both rural and urban India. The first NPE was propagated by the Government of India by Prime Minister Indira Gandhi in 1968, the second by Prime Minister Rajiv Gandhi in 1986 and the third by Prime Minister

“Vision of Future Education”

Narendra Modi in 2020. The National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020), which was approved by the Union Cabinet of India on 29 July 2020, outlines the vision of India's new education system. The NEP 2020 enacts numerous changes in India's education policy. It aims to increase state expenditure on education from around 4% to 6% of the GDP as soon as possible. In January 2015, a committee under former Cabinet Secretary T. S. R. Subramanian started the consultation process for the New Education Policy. Based on the committee report, in June 2017, the draft NEP was submitted in 2019 by a panel led by former Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO) chief Krishnaswamy Kasturirangan. The Draft New Education Policy (DNEP) 2019, was later released by Ministry of Human Resource Development, followed by a number of public consultations. The new NEP has been introduced with an aim to formalize changes in the system from school level to college/university level. The new education policy must help re-establish teachers, at all levels, as the most respected and essential members of our society, because they truly shape our next generation of citizens. It must do everything to empower teachers and help them to do their job as effectively as possible. The new education policy must help recruit the very best and brightest to enter the teaching profession at all levels, by ensuring livelihood, respect, dignity, and autonomy, while also instilling in the system basic methods of quality control and accountability.

Objectives of the study

The primary objective of this research is to study the impact of New Education Policy 2020 on Teacher education. The study also outlines the salient features of NEP and analyses how they affect the existing education system.

Research methodology

This research is a descriptive study. The necessary secondary data was collected from various websites including those of Government of India, magazines, journals, other publications, etc. This data was then analyzed and reviewed to arrive at the inferences and conclusions.

SALIENT FEATURES OF NEP RELATED TO TEACHER EDUCATION

There are a lot of reforms and new developments which have been introduced by NEP in the teacher education sector. Some of the salient features are:

- All schools of foundation, preparatory, middle, and secondary level should appoint 4-years

“Vision of Future Education”

integrated B.Ed. degree holders as teachers with dual major specialization (Education & Subject).

- All teacher education programmes to be conducted within composite multidisciplinary institutions and stringent action to be taken against substandard stand- alone Teacher Education Institutions.
- Online computerized system for teacher transfers to ensure Transparency. Technology based planning and forecasting of teacher recruitment to assess expected subject- wise vacancies over next two decades.
- Teacher Eligibility Tests for all teachers across Foundational, Preparatory, Middle and Secondary stage in both Public and Private Schools will be strengthened
- Subject score from TET or NTA tests and classroom demonstration to be taken into account for recruitment of subject teachers.
- Shorter local teacher education programmes to be available at BITEs and DIETs, or at school complexes for eminent local persons who can be hired to teach at schools as master instructors for promoting local professions, knowledge and skills. Eg, local art. Music. Agriculture, business, sports, carpentry and other vocational crafts. Shorter post B.Ed Courses will also be available.
- Merit based tenure track system and minimum 50 hours of continuous professional development for teacher professional development.
- Teachers doing outstanding work must be recognized, promoted and given salary raised. Incentivize all teachers to do their best work.
- Career growth to be available for teachers within a single stage that is foundational, preparatory, Middle or Secondary. National Professional Standards for teachers by 2022.
- Academic leadership positions to be made available for outstanding teachers with leadership and management skills.
- New and comprehensive National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education to be introduced by 2021 and NTA Testing for admission to B.Ed.
- National Higher Education Regulatory Council (NHERC) to function as single point regulator for higher education sector including Teacher Education.
- All stand-alone Teachers Education Institutions should convert themselves as Multi-disciplinary HETs by 2030 to offer only four years integrated B.Ed. programme.

“Vision of Future Education”

- Setting up of National Mission for Mentoring with a large pool of outstanding senior retired faculty.
- A comprehensive teacher recruitment planning exercise will be conducted across India and in each state over next two decades.
- The practice of hiring new Para- teachers will eventually be phased out.
- A technology based comprehensive teacher requirement planning forecasting exercise to be conducted by each state.
- Teachers to have more autonomy in choosing aspects of pedagogy in classroom teaching.
- Promotion and salary increase will not occur based on the length of tenure/ seniority but on the basis of appraisal.
- The National Council for Teacher Education will come under the GEC, as a professional standard setting body (PSSB).
- M.Ed. will be one year with research focus. The faculty profile in Departments of Education will be diverse with Ph.D.'s in different areas.
- All interested senior or retired faculty will be utilized short or long term for guiding, mentoring, or professional support for research/training/innovation. A separate National Mission for Mentoring will be established.
- To prevent the large amounts of time spent currently by teachers on non-teaching activities, teachers will not be engaged any longer in work that is not directly related to teaching;
- A system of multiple parameters for proper assessment of performance will be developed for the same by State that is based on peer reviews, attendance, commitment, and hours of CPD etc.

DETAILED ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF NEP ON TEACHER EDUCATION

Pre-Service Teacher Education

Based on the recommendations of NEP 2020 on teacher education and training, a National Curriculum Framework for Teacher Education, NCFTE 2021 will be drafted to guide all teacher education, pre-service and in-service, of teachers working in academic, vocational & special education streams.

The 4-year integrated B.Ed., the minimal degree qualification for schoolteachers, is conceived as a multidisciplinary and integrated dual-major bachelor's degree, in Education as well as a specialized subject. The admission to this course shall be through suitable subject and aptitude

“Vision of Future Education”

tests conducted by the National Testing Agency (NTA). All multidisciplinary Universities have been directed to set-up an education department and run B.Ed. programmes in collaboration with their other departments. Shorter post-B.Ed. certification courses will also be available for career growth of teachers who wish to move into more specialized areas. All fresh Ph.D. entrants, will be required to take credit-based courses in teaching/education/pedagogy/writing related to their chosen Ph.D. subject during their doctoral training period .

It proposes several reforms like this to empower teachers and ‘restore the high respect and status’ to this profession hoping that it would eventually attract the best minds and talent to choose teaching as their profession.

Teacher Recruitment & Employment

For recruitment in private or government school the teacher must qualify through TET, give a demonstration class, pass the interview, and have knowledge of local language(s). The NEP 2020 provides – Teacher Eligibility Tests (TETs) will now be extended to cover teachers across all the new stages (Foundational, Preparatory, Middle and Secondary) of school education For subject teachers, TET as well as NTA test scores in the corresponding subjects will also be considered for recruitment.

The NEP 2020 also encourages special shorter local teacher education programmes at BITEs, DIETs, or at school complexes themselves for eminent local persons who can be hired to teach at schools or school complexes as ‘master instructors’, for the purpose of promoting local professions, knowledge, and skills, e.g., local art, music, agriculture, business, sports, carpentry, and other vocational crafts.

Since teaching is one of the low-paid professions in India, experiential learning and concept-oriented teaching will be a challenging task. Until the teacher remuneration is revised, the implementation of the NEP 2020 will be quite challenging. But NEP doesn’t discuss about preservice or in-service teacher education conducting in DIET.

The policy is not clear about the working conditions and salaries of these ‘local’ teachers, nor is there any clarity about who will hire them. The idea of ‘contract teachers’ or ‘para teachers’ slipped into educational practice in the 1990s without any policy-level approval.

Teaching Career & Professionalism

“Vision of Future Education”

The NEP 2020 talks of creating performance standards for teachers clearly spelling out the role of the teacher at different levels of expertise/stage and competencies required for that stage.

By 2022 a set of National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST) will be created that will determine all aspects of teacher career management, including tenure, continuous professional development efforts, salary increases, promotions, and other recognitions.

NEP 2020 also talks of Teacher Audit or Performance Appraisals that will be carried at regular intervals. These standards for performance appraisal, will also be formulated. Henceforth, promotions and salary increases will not occur based on the length of tenure or seniority, but only based on such appraisal. School teachers must undergo 50 hours of CPD opportunities every year to keep themselves by attending workshops or on-line teacher development modules. School Principals too must undergo CPD in modules related to leadership, school management and for implementing competency-based learning.

In addition, International pedagogical approaches will be studied by NCERT, identified, and recommended for assimilation in pedagogical practices in India through CPD.

To have uniformity in professional standards for teachers, a single umbrella body like NPST was always a requirement and this has been a vision of numerous educationists. This is considered as the right step in streamlining education policy. Also continuous professional development for teachers as well as Principals is a must and I welcoming it. But promotions and salary increases is based on peer appraisal as per NEP- 2020. It should be reviewed I think.

FURTHER SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT

1. The student selection process for primary teacher education involves two stages: an examination to assess applicants’ academic learning skills; and a combination of written questions and aptitude tests to assess applicants’ skills, motivation and commitment.
2. Ph.D. should be a compulsory qualification for a permanent teaching position in Colleges & Universities
3. All primary schools must provide swimming and water safety lessons and it should be included in the curriculum of student teachers of primary education.
4. Appoint Special Educators in primary schools too to provide inclusive education to IEDC students.

CONCLUSION

The culture and community of teachers will remain upright and reputable as the commitment for professionalism, and career-focused factors will motivate the teachers to stay updated in terms of characteristics, vocational skills, academics and personality building. The enthusiasm in teachers for learning from peer-practitioners and upskilling every learning to an innovative form of teaching with the introduction of the policy will rise. Thus, the ones who shape the path of children will with a better determination also frame their paths with an intention to leap skills and have its impression on their students' bright future. These traits in a teacher will begin to imbibe from an early stage of training to get a qualitative stance and efficient plan of action aiding the entire system. Hence, NEP opens the door of evolution for teacher's fraternity in India to be vocal and get global! Thus, the NEP 2020 lays emphasis on making the education system holistic, flexible and aligned to the needs of 21st-century education. However, in order to accomplish all these goals, we must overcome all the execution challenges in a sustained manner for years to come.

REFERENCES

- Aithal, P. S.; Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna (2019). "Analysis of Higher Education in Indian National
- Education Policy Proposal 2019 and Its Implementation Challenges". International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters. 3 (2): 1–35. SSRN 3417517
- Nandini, ed. (29 July 2020). "New Education Policy 2020 Highlights: School and higher education to see major changes". Hindustan Times.
- Jebaraj, Priscilla (2 August 2020). "The Hindu Explains | What has the National Education Policy 2020 proposed?". The Hindu. ISSN 0971-751X
- Chopra, Ritika (2 August 2020). "Explained: Reading the new National Education Policy 2020". The Indian Express.
- Rohatgi, Anubha, ed. (7 August 2020). "Highlights | NEP will play role in reducing gap between research and education in India: PM Modi". Hindustan Times.
- Krishna, Atul (29 July 2020). "NEP 2020 Highlights: School And Higher Education". NDTV. Naidu, M. Venkaiah (8 August 2020). "The New Education Policy 2020 is set to be a landmark in India's history of education". Times of India Blog. https://static.pib.gov.in/WriteReadData/userfiles/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf

“Vision of Future Education”

- <https://www.orfonline.org/expert-speak/national-education-policy-2020-policy-times/>
- <https://www.highereducationdigest.com/the-impact-of-national-education-policy-2020-on-professional-education/>
 - <http://bweducation.businessworld.in/article/NEP-2020-Impact-On-Higher-Education-/07-08-2020-305999/>
 - <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/readersblog/theaitics/implications-of-the-national-education-policy-2020-on-higher-education-in-india-2-24729/>
 - <https://www.hindustantimes.com/india-news/pm-modi-s-address-at-conclave-on-transformational-reforms-in-higher-education-under-national-education-policy-highlights/storydehOW8q8ZRrONbbFSRjg0H.html>
 - NEP (National Education Policy) 2020. New Delhi: Ministry of Human Resource Development. Ramachandran, Vimala, Deepa Das, Ganesh Nigam, and Anjali Shandilya. (Forth coming) 2020. 'Contract Teachers in India: Recent Trends and Current Status'. Research Report. Azim Premji University, Bangalore.
 - Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, Shubhrajyotsna (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards Achieving its Objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 19-41. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3988767>.
